

Water management

Yield and water use efficiency of newly developed rice mutants under different water management practices

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We tested the effects of water management on newly developed rice mutants BINA 4-39-15-13 and BINA 4-5-17-19. Practices tested were continuous ponding (5 ± 22 cm water) and application of 5 cm water at 3, 5, and 7 d after disappearance of ponded water (DAP).

At final land preparation, each plot was fertilized uniformly with a basal dose of 60 kg N/ha as urea, 26.4 kg P/ha as triple superphosphate, 33.2 kg K/ha as muriate of potash, 10 kg S/ha as gypsum, and 4 kg Zn/ha as zinc oxide. Another 20 kg N/ha (as urea) was topdressed, half at active vegetative phase and half at flowering.

The experiment was laid out in a split-plot design. Forty-five-d-old seedlings were planted in a sandy loam soil at the BINA farm the first week of Feb 1992. Irrigation was applied in main plot treatments (5- x 6-m plots) and in rice mutant subplot treatments (5- x 3-m plots). We applied 3-5 cm water to all treatment plots for the first 2 wk to allow for crop establishment and then irrigation treatments were followed. BINA 4-39-15-13 was harvested the third week of May, and BINA 4-5-17-19 was harvested 15 d later.

Continuous ponding required about 214% more water for irrigation than the other treatments, but produced only 13, 15, and 15% more grain than when 5 cm water was applied at 3, 5, and 7 DAP, respectively (see table).

BINA 4-5-17-19 produced significantly more grain (8.1t/ha), straw, and tillers/plant, than BINA 4-39-15-13 (7.5 t/ha). The 7 DAP treatment required the least water and had the highest water use efficiency (see table) and is recommended for areas where water is costly. Yield, however, was 1.1 t/ha less than under continuous ponding. ■

Number of irrigations, water requirement, and water use efficiency of rice mutants under different water management practices. BINA Farm, Mymensingh, Bangladesh, 1992 dry season.

Treatment	Irrigation (no.)	Amount of irrigation water ^a	Water requirement (cm)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Straw yield (t/ha)	Water use efficiency (kg/ha per cm)
Continuous ponding (5 ± 2 cm water)	Almost every other day	220	273.95	8.6	7.0	36.10
Application of water 3 DAP ^b	7	70	87.95	7.7	6.4	86.98
Application of water 5 DAP	7	70	87.95	7.5	6.2	85.04
Application of water 7 DAP	5	60	77.95	7.5	6.9	95.95

^a Includes 30 cm of water for crop establishment. Amount of rainfall is 17.95 cm. ^bDAP = d after disappearance of ponded water

Farming systems

Identification of recommendation domains for technology generation and transfer in rice culture

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We conducted a study to identify the recommendation domains for the technology generation and transfer processes in the coastal rice-growing agroecological zone of Matara district, Sri Lanka. Exploratory studies were carried out during 1990-91 wet season and 1991 dry season to understand prevailing production conditions. A random sample

of 291 farmers were surveyed using a pretested questionnaire to identify production problems.

Saline soil, acidic soil, water deficit, and excess water were identified as problems. All vary according to elevation.

The area was classified into three domains: upper (>1 msl), intermediate (1-0 msl), and lower (>0 ms1). An index (based on a scoring procedure) was constructed to estimate intensity of the problem. Farmers were located on this scale. Scores were divided into four categories. Actual score for a particular problem was presented as a percentage and assigned an intensity category (see table).

Study locations can be classified into three recommendation domains on the

Three recommendation domains based on production conditions. Matara district, Sri Lanka.

Recommendation domain	Farmers (no.)	Sample size (no.)	Intensity of problems (%)			
			Soil acidification	Soil salinization	Water deficit	Excess water
Upper	2562	126	76-100 (very high)	na	76-100 (very high)	na
Intermediate	1771	89	26-50 (moderate)	na	51-75 (high)	
Lower	1504	76	0-25 (low)	51-75 (high)	na	51-75 (high)

^a na = not applicable

basis of constraints prevailing in rice production. The upper domain experiences severe water deficit and soil

acidification whereas the lower domain has excess water and soil salinization. Technology generation processes, such as

varietal improvement programs, need to make location-specific recommendations for the identified domains. ■

Postharvest technology

Delay in threshing and mode of beating effects on milling recovery

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Harvested rice in the Punjab, Pakistan, is usually left in the field to dry in loose bundles for a few days before threshing. We assessed how a delay in threshing affected milling recovery of commercial

varieties KS282 (medium grain) and Basmati 385 (fine grain) from 1988 to 1990. We compared the traditional hand-threshing techniques of beating rice against a bund, steel drum, or wooden log.

The rice was harvested at the optimum maturity stage and left in the field in loose bundles of uniform size (40 plants, with about 20 tillers/plant) for 0, 2, 4, and 6 d before threshing. The difference in day and night temperature was about

15°C, which resulted in repeated drying and wetting of the rice. Rice samples were sun-dried to the optimum moisture content and milled.

Threshing grain on the day of harvest gave the highest head rice recovery and the lowest broken rice (see table). The recovery decreased with delay in threshing. The differences between delays of 0 and 2 d were not significant in either variety (see table). Differences in mode of beating did not significantly affect milling recovery. ■

Milling recovery at different threshing times and modes of beating. Punjab, Pakistan, 1988-90. ^a

Delay in threshing after harvesting (d)	Head rice (%)					Broken rice (%)				
	Beating on bund	Beating on steel drum	Beating on wooden log	Mean	Decrease in head rice	Beating on bund	Beating on steel drum	Beating on wooden log	Mean	Increase in broken rice
<i>KS282</i>										
0	55.7	56.0	55.6	55.8 a	—	15.0	14.6	16.0	15.2 a	—
2	55.3	55.7	54.9	55.3 a	0.5	15.7	15.8	17.0	16.2 a	1.0
4	53.0	53.5	52.7	53.1 b	2.7	17.4	18.0	18.6	18.0 b	2.8
6	49.6	49.0	49.5	49.4 c	6.4	21.0	22.0	21.2	21.4 c	6.2
Mean	53.4 a	53.5 a	53.2 a	—	—	17.3 a	17.6 a	18.2 a	—	—
<i>Basmati 385</i>										
0	53.0	52.5	53.3	52.9 a	—	17.0	16.7	16.8	16.8 a	—
2	52.1	52.0	52.5	52.2 a	0.7	17.3	18.0	17.7	17.7 a	0.9
4	49.6	50.4	51.0	50.3 b	2.6	20.0	19.8	18.0	19.3 b	2.5
6	47.0	47.2	46.5	46.9 c	6.0	23.0	22.6	22.6	22.7 c	5.9
Mean	50.4 a	50.5 a	50.8 a	—	—	19.3 a	19.3 a	19.2 a	—	—

^a Results are av of 3 yr Means in a column followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level

Announcements

Outstanding young women in rice science award

The Outstanding Young Women in Rice Science (OYWRS) Award is the foremost international recognition of the important contributions women are making to rice research and agriculture. The biennial award was established in 1990 by IRRI to encourage the participation of women in rice research and to promote their professional development.

Presentation of award

The 1994 presentation will be part of the International Rice Research Conference (IRRC), tentatively set for April 1994 in Los Baños, Laguna, Philippines. Awardees receive a recognition plaque and a travel grant to attend IRRC. Each awardee must present a scientific paper on her research.

Criteria

The award is presented to individuals who are 40 years of age or younger (born on 1 Jan 1954 or later for the 1994 program) and actively conducting research in any endeavor of rice science in a public or private institution in the five regions of the world's major rice-producing areas. Recipients are selected by regions: Africa, South Asia, West Asia, Southeast Asia, and Latin America and the Caribbean. Awards are made